

Joint Polarization and Spatial Modulation Using Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface

Emad Ibrahim, Rickard Nilsson, and Jaap van de Beek

Department of Computer Science, Electrical and Space Engineering,
Luleå University of Technology, Sweden.
{emad.farouk.ibrahim, rickard.o.nilsson, jaap.vandebeek}@ltu.se

Abstract—We propose a joint polarization and spatial modulation (JPSM) scheme using reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS). In this scheme, a RIS equipped with dual-polarized (DP) reflecting elements is used to assist the communication between a transmitter of a single polarized antenna and a receiver equipped with a uniform linear array of DP antennas, while additionally encoding the reflected waves on the RIS to perform JPSM scheme. The information data is encoded in terms of the receiver DP antenna index as well as the polarization state of the received signal. Furthermore, we develop exhaustive and heuristic RIS phase shift design solutions to enable the RIS-JPSM scheme. Moreover, both an optimum maximum likelihood and a low complexity greedy detectors are formulated. The proposed scheme enhances the data rate by operating higher-order polarization modulation in comparison to the conventional RIS-based spatial modulation scheme.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable intelligent surface, polarization modulation, and spatial modulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) has been widely introduced as an emerging technology for several wireless applications. A RIS is a thin planar surface that contains many low-cost and nearly passive reflecting elements each of which can induce a real-time controllable reflection coefficient to the incident waves. Thus, the RIS creates a configurable propagation environment which introduces it as a solution for different applications such as coverage enhancement, wireless channel rank improvement, and localization [1].

A potential function of the RIS is that it can configure the polarization state of the reflected waves on it [2]. The polarization defines the orientation of the electric field relative to the direction of propagation. The polarization dimension provides additional degrees of freedom to the wireless channel similar to the time, frequency, and space dimensions [3]. RIS polarization configuration becomes possible thanks to the deployment of dual-polarized (DP) reflecting elements [4] which could excite two orthogonal polarization states and induce independent reflection coefficients for each polarization state [5].

One of the promising applications of the RIS is to act as a modulator for information wherein the RIS not only enhances the communication performance between a transmitter and

receiver, using its beamforming capability but also modulates the reflected wave with additional data. Toward this goal, [6] proposed a RIS that switches the states of its elements between on and off, to perform amplitude shift keying modulation while [7], [8] proposed a RIS-based spatial modulation (RIS-SM) scheme, wherein the information is encoded in terms of the transmitter and/or receiver antenna indices. Furthermore, [9], [10], proposed RIS-based reflecting modulation wherein the additional information is encoded by the reflection patterns of the RIS. Moreover, [11] proposed RIS-assisted binary polarization modulation for line-of-sight environments wherein the polarization dimension is exploited for data modulation.

In this paper, we propose a RIS-based joint polarization and spatial modulation (RIS-JPSM) scheme where a RIS of DP elements is deployed to assist the communication between a transmitter of a single polarization (SP) antenna and a receiver equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) of DP antennas when the direct link is blocked. In addition to the passive beamforming of the RIS, it jointly performs spatial and polarization modulation along the reflected waves.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows. First, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that proposes a RIS-JPSM scheme. Second, we employ and highlight a channel model that includes all the possible polarization and spatial impairments including the cross-polarization isolation (XPI) of the transmitter, RIS, and receiver, the geometric orientation difference between the transmitter and RIS as well as between the RIS and receiver, the cross-polarization discrimination (XPD) of the wireless channel, and the polarization as well as the spatial correlations. Third, we propose exhaustive and heuristic RIS phase shift design solutions to allow the RIS-JPSM. Finally, we formulate both an optimum maximum likelihood and a low-complexity greedy detectors.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Signal Model

We consider the communication between a SP transmitter antenna and a receiver equipped with a ULA of N DP antennas, where a RIS of L DP reflecting elements is deployed to assist the communications when the direct channel between the transmitter and the receiver is blocked [7], [8]. Additionally, the RIS encodes the reflected wave performing JPSM to enhance the data rate. Each RIS element comprises

two independent sub-elements representing the vertical and horizontal polarization states, generating two distinct reflection coefficients for both polarizations [4]. In this scenario, the received signal at the receiver array becomes

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{G}\Psi\mathbf{h}x_k + \mathbf{w}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{y} = [\mathbf{y}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N^T]^T$ such as $\mathbf{y}_n = [y_{n_v}, y_{n_h}]^T$ with y_{n_v} and y_{n_h} denote the received signal at the vertical and horizontal branches of the n th DP antenna in the receiver array, respectively. Furthermore, $x_k \in \{x_1, \dots, x_K\}$ denotes transmitted symbol generated from a phase shift keying (PSK) modulation scheme of K distinct symbols such that $\mathbb{E}[|x_k|^2] = P_t$, with P_t denotes the transmitted power, $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^{2N_r \times 1}$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) as $\mathbf{w} \sim \mathcal{C}_N(0, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{2N_r})$, with σ^2 denoting the noise variance. Each RIS element induces two independent phase shifts along the vertical and horizontal polarization states denoted for the l th RIS element as ϕ_{l_v} and ϕ_{l_h} , respectively. Thus, the RIS phase shift matrix becomes $\Psi = \text{diag}\{\phi\}$, where $\phi = [\bar{\phi}_1^T, \dots, \bar{\phi}_L^T]^T$ with $\bar{\phi}_l = [e^{j\phi_{l_v}}, e^{j\phi_{l_h}}]^T$ contains the phase shifts of the l th RIS element.

Furthermore, $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{2N \times 2M}$ represents the channel between the RIS and receiver array which can be structured as $\mathbf{G} = [\mathbf{G}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{G}_N^T]^T$, where $\mathbf{G}_n \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2M}$ characterizes the channel between the RIS and the n th DP receiver antenna. Specifically, $\mathbf{G}_n = [\mathbf{g}_{n_v}, \mathbf{g}_{n_h}]^T$ with $\mathbf{g}_{n_v} \in \mathbb{C}^{2M \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{g}_{n_h} \in \mathbb{C}^{2M \times 1}$ represent the channel between the RIS to the vertical and horizontal branches in the n th DP receiver antenna such as $\mathbf{g}_{n_v} = [\mathbf{g}_{n_v,1}^T, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{n_v,L}^T]^T$ with $\mathbf{g}_{n_v,l} = [g_{n_v,l_v}, g_{n_v,l_h}]^T$ denotes the channel between the vertical antenna branch to the l th RIS element. Similarly, $\mathbf{g}_{n_h} = [\mathbf{g}_{n_h,1}^T, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{n_h,L}^T]^T$ with $\mathbf{g}_{n_h,l} = [g_{n_h,l_v}, g_{n_h,l_h}]^T$ denotes the channel between the horizontal antenna branch to the l th RIS element. Moreover, $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{2L \times 1}$ denotes the channel between the SP antenna at the transmitter and RIS as $\mathbf{h} = [\bar{\mathbf{h}}_1^T, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{h}}_L^T]^T$, where $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_l = [h_{l_v}, h_{l_h}]^T$ with h_{l_v} , and h_{l_h} denote the channel along the vertical and horizontal states of the l th element.

B. Channel Model

First, we consider the wireless channel between the transmitter and a particular DP RIS element. Then, we develop the channel over the whole RIS including the spatial correlation among different RIS elements. The wireless channel between the transmitter and the l th DP RIS element can be defined as [12], [13]

$$\bar{\mathbf{h}}_l = \mathbf{F}_{ris} \bar{\mathbf{Z}}_l \mathbf{A}_t \mathbf{f}_t, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{F}_{ris} account for the XPI of the RIS element representing the cross-talk that occurs between the vertical and horizontal sub-elements as

$$\mathbf{F}_{ris} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \chi_{ris}}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sqrt{\chi_{ris}} e^{j\varphi_{ris}} \\ -\sqrt{\chi_{ris}} e^{j\varphi_{ris}} & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where χ_{ris}^{-1} and φ_{ris} are the XPI factor and the phase offset of the RIS element, respectively. Similarly, $\mathbf{f}_t = (1/\sqrt{1 + \chi_t})[1, -\sqrt{\chi_t} e^{j\varphi_t}]^T$ account for the XPI of the transmitter with χ_t^{-1} , φ_t denoting the XPI factor and the phase

offset of the SP antenna at the transmitter, respectively. \mathbf{A}_t is a rotation matrix that accounts for the geometric orientation difference between the SP antenna at the transmitter and the DP element in the RIS as

$$\mathbf{A}_t = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_t) & -\sin(\theta_t) \\ \sin(\theta_t) & \cos(\theta_t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $\theta_t \in [0, 2\pi]$ is a rotation angle indicating the geometric orientation difference. Note that \mathbf{F}_{ris} and \mathbf{f}_t depend mainly on the electromagnetic (EM) characteristics of the DP RIS element and the transmitter antenna, respectively. On the other hand, $\bar{\mathbf{Z}}_l$ is a random channel matrix accounts for the DP signal propagation in the wireless channel as

$$\bar{\mathbf{Z}}_l = \mathbf{C}_{pris}^{\frac{1}{2}} \bar{\mathbf{W}}_l \mathbf{C}_{pt}^{\frac{1}{2}} \odot \Sigma_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{z}_{l_{vv}} & \bar{z}_{l_{vh}} \\ \bar{z}_{l_{hv}} & \bar{z}_{l_{hh}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where \odot denotes the Hadamard product and $\bar{\mathbf{W}}_l \sim \mathcal{C}_N(0, \mathbf{I}_2)$ account for the small scale fading of the wireless channel. While, \mathbf{C}_{pris} and \mathbf{C}_{pt} represent the RIS and transmitter polarization correlation matrices as

$$\mathbf{C}_{pris} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & p_{ris} \\ p_{ris}^* & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{C}_{pt} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & p_t \\ p_t^* & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where p_{ris} and p_t denote the correlation coefficients at the RIS and transmitter, respectively.

On the other hand, Σ_1 account for the XPD of the wireless channel between the transmitter and RIS element arising from the reflections, scattering and diffraction that occur in the wireless channel. The XPD measures the average amount of discrimination in the wireless channel over two orthogonal polarization waves as $\kappa_1 = \mathbb{E}[|\bar{z}_{l_{vv}}|^2]/\mathbb{E}[|\bar{z}_{l_{hv}}|^2] = \mathbb{E}[|\bar{z}_{l_{hh}}|^2]/\mathbb{E}[|\bar{z}_{l_{vh}}|^2]$, where κ_1 is the XPD factor of the channel between the transmitter and the RIS. By denoting $\mathbb{E}[|\bar{z}_{l_{vv}}|^2] = q_1$ and $\mathbb{E}[|\bar{z}_{l_{vh}}|^2] = 1 - q_1$, the XPD matrix can be defined as

$$\Sigma_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{1 - q_1} & \sqrt{q_1} \\ \sqrt{q_1} & \sqrt{1 - q_1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $q_1 = 1/(1 + \kappa_1)$ such as $0 \leq q_1 \leq 1$ indicates the amount of leakage from one polarization to the other due to the depolarization of the EM wave in the wireless channel.

However, note that the wireless channel becomes spatially correlated due to the small separation distances between the elements in the RIS. Thus, to include the impact of spatial correlation across different RIS elements, the channel vector between the transmitter and the whole RIS element can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{h} = (\mathbf{I}_L \otimes \mathbf{F}_{ris}) \mathbf{Z}_1 \mathbf{A}_t \mathbf{f}_t, \quad (8)$$

where \otimes denotes the Kronecker product, while \mathbf{F}_{ris} and \mathbf{A}_t are assumed to be fixed for the whole RIS given that it is structured from elements of identical characteristics and the RIS is deployed in the far-field relative to the transmitter and receiver. In addition, to include the spatial correlation, the random channel matrix can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{Z}_1 = ((\mathbf{R}_{ris} \otimes \mathbf{C}_{pris})^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{C}_{pt}^{\frac{1}{2}}) \odot (\mathbf{I}_L \otimes \Sigma_1), \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_1 = [\bar{\mathbf{W}}_1^T, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{W}}_L^T]^T$ and $\mathbf{R}_{ris} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times L}$ is the spatial correlation matrix. Without loss of generality, we assume a square-shaped RIS with \sqrt{L} elements stacked both along the y -axis and the z -axis. Furthermore, we utilize the exponential spatial correlation model [14]; with $\mathbf{R}_{ris} = \mathbf{R}_{ris_y} \otimes \mathbf{R}_{ris_z}$, where $\mathbf{R}_{ris_y} \in \mathbb{C}^{\sqrt{L} \times \sqrt{L}}$ denotes the spatial correlation along the y -axis as $[\mathbf{R}_{ris_y}]_{a,b} = \delta_{ris_y}^{|a-b|}$, where $[\mathbf{R}_{ris_y}]_{a,b}$ denotes the element in the a th row and b th column of \mathbf{R}_{ris_y} . Similarly, $\mathbf{R}_{ris_z} \in \mathbb{C}^{\sqrt{L} \times \sqrt{L}}$ denotes the spatial correlation along the z -axis, where $[\mathbf{R}_{ris_z}]_{a,b} = \delta_{ris_z}^{|a-b|}$ with $0 \leq \delta_{ris_y}, \delta_{ris_z} \leq 1$ are the spatial correlation coefficients along the y and z axes, respectively.

Similarly, the wireless channel between the RIS and the receiver of N DP receiving antennas can be defined as

$$\mathbf{G} = (\mathbf{I}_N \otimes \mathbf{F}_r) \mathbf{Z}_2 \mathbf{A}_{ris} \mathbf{F}_{ris}, \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{F}_r account for the XPI of the DP receiver antennas response which has a similar form to (3) but in terms of the XPI factor and phase offset of the receiver denoted as χ_r^{-1} and φ_r , respectively. Furthermore, \mathbf{A}_{ris} is the rotation matrix that accounts for the geometric orientation difference between the RIS and receiver which has a similar form to (4) but in terms of the rotation angles denoted as θ_{ris} . Moreover, $\mathbf{Z}_2 \in \mathbb{C}^{2N \times 2L}$ is a random matrix accounting for the DP signal propagation in the wireless channel as

$$\mathbf{Z}_2 = ((\mathbf{R}_r \otimes \mathbf{C}_{p_r})^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{W}_2 (\mathbf{R}_{ris} \otimes \mathbf{C}_{p_{ris}})^{\frac{1}{2}}) \odot (\mathbf{1}_N \otimes \mathbf{\Sigma}_2), \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_2 \in \mathbb{C}^{2N \times 2M}$ of i.i.d. $\sim \mathcal{C}_N(0, 1)$ entries, \mathbf{C}_{p_r} is the receiver polarization correlation matrix which has a similar form (6) but in the receiver polarization correlation coefficient denoted as p_r , $\mathbf{R}_r \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is the receiver spatial correlation matrix; by considering exponential correlation model $[\mathbf{R}_r]_{a,b} = \delta_r^{|a-b|}$, where δ_r is the receiver spatial correlation coefficient, and $\mathbf{\Sigma}_2$ account for the XPD which has a similar form to (7) but in terms q_2 and the XPD factor κ_2 of the RIS to receiver channel.

III. JOINT POLARIZATION AND SPATIAL MODULATION

The RIS is deployed to support the communications from the SP antenna of K PSK transmitter while also superimposing additional information bits along the reflected waves to enhance the overall data rate. In particular, the RIS encodes the reflected waves to perform spatial modulation in terms of the receiver antenna indices; thus, allows $\log_2[N]$ additional bits. In addition, the RIS encodes the polarization state of the received signal at the chosen receiver antenna index to perform polarization modulation. Therefore, given a polarization modulation scheme of M distinct symbols, the RIS-JPSM scheme allows the transmission of $\log_2[M] + \log_2[N] + \log_2[K]$ bits per channel use (bpcu).

The received signal at a particular antenna index can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{y}_n = \bar{\mathbf{G}}_n \bar{\mathbf{\Psi}} \mathbf{h} x_k + \mathbf{w}_n = \boldsymbol{\mu}_n + \mathbf{w}_n, \quad (12)$$

where the DP noiseless signal denoted as $\boldsymbol{\mu}_n = [\mu_{n_v}, \mu_{n_h}]^T$ can be reformulated as

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_n = \sum_{l=1}^L \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{n_v,l}^T \bar{\Psi}_l \bar{\mathbf{h}}_l \\ \mathbf{g}_{n_h,l}^T \bar{\Psi}_l \bar{\mathbf{h}}_l \end{bmatrix} x_k, \quad (13)$$

where $\bar{\Psi}_l = \text{diag}\{\bar{\phi}_l\}$ represents the tuning matrix of the l th RIS element. Note from (13) that JPSM is possible by controlling the RIS phase shifts. In the next subsections, we provide a fundamental background on the polarization of EM waves as well as the polarization modulation. Then, we illustrate a RIS algorithm to perform joint spatial and polarization modulation.

A. Polarization Modulation

The polarization state of an EM wave is described using two parameters, the first is the amplitude ratio between the complex vertical and horizontal components while the second is their relative phase difference [3]. The Stokes vector is a fundamental tool that offers a graphical description of the state of polarization. The Stokes vector of a DP signal denoted as $\mathbf{e} = [e_v, e_h]^T$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{s}_e = \begin{bmatrix} s_{e_0} \\ s_{e_1} \\ s_{e_2} \\ s_{e_3} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} |e_H|^2 + |e_V|^2 \\ |e_H|^2 - |e_V|^2 \\ 2\Re\{e_H e_V^*\} \\ -2\Im\{e_H e_V^*\} \end{bmatrix} = s_{e_0} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \cos 2\vartheta \\ \sin 2\vartheta \cos \beta \\ \sin 2\vartheta \sin \beta \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where $\Re\{\cdot\}$, $\Im\{\cdot\}$, and $\{\cdot\}^*$ denote the real and imaginary parts, and the complex conjugate, respectively. In addition, $\vartheta = \arctan(|e_v|/|e_h|)$ and $\beta = \arg\{e_v\} - \arg\{e_h\}$ are the amplitude ratio and the phase difference between the vertical and horizontal components, respectively. Furthermore, s_{e_0} represents the energy of the signal and $\bar{\mathbf{s}}_e = [s_{e_1}, s_{e_2}, s_{e_3}]^T$ denotes the Stokes sub-vector which represent the state of polarization of the signal and allows its Cartesian mapping into the three-dimensional Poincaré sphere.

The Poincaré space offers an important geometrical interpretation of the state of polarization of EM waves. In Fig. 1, the Poincaré sphere is shown where every possible polarization state can be represented by a distinct point on the sphere. Any two polarization states are orthogonal to each other if the line connecting them passes through the origin. Left and right-hand circular polarization states are represented by the north and south poles of the sphere on the s_3 -axis, respectively. In addition, the vertical and horizontal polarization states are

Fig. 1: Poincaré sphere.

indicated on the s_1 -axis, while $+45^\circ$ and -45° polarization state are indicated on the s_2 -axis. Moreover, the polarization state is fully described using the amplitude ratio and phase difference where 2ϑ is the angle between the polarization state and s_1 -axis, while β is the angle between the polarization state projection on $s_2 - s_3$ plane and s_2 -axis as shown in Fig. 1.

The polarization modulation encodes the data in terms of the polarization state of the EM waves. In this scheme, the constellation diagram is represented by distinct points on the Poincaré sphere. The symbol mapping process is to allocate for every data symbol a distinct polarization state in terms of the amplitude ratio and phase difference tuple denoted as $\xi = \{\vartheta, \beta\}$. The symbol mapping scheme is beyond the scope of this paper. However, we rely on a mapping scheme which maximizes the minimum distance between any two distinct symbols on the Poincaré sphere [15], which is known as the sphere packing problem and has particular solutions till 128PolSK [16]. In this mapping scheme, the binary polarization shift keying (BPolSK) symbols are mapped to any two orthogonal polarization states; i.e., the vertical and horizontal polarization states. The quadrature PolSK (QPolSK) becomes the vertices of a regular tetrahedron inside the Poincaré sphere.

B. RIS Phase Shift Design

The RIS phase shift design allows controlling the amplitude ratio and the phase difference between the vertical and horizontal received signal at a particular antenna index in the receiver ULA. Thus, we design the phases of the RIS to perform superimposed polarization modulation along the conventional spatial modulation, which is achieved by mapping the data symbol to a particular antenna index.

Consider a polarization modulation scheme with M distinct symbols, where each symbol can be described with the tuple $\xi_m = \{\vartheta_m, \beta_m\}, \forall m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$. From (13), we can notice that the phase shifts of a particular DP RIS element $\bar{\Psi}_l$ impacts both the received signal at the vertical and horizontal branch; thus, the RIS phase shift design is non-trivial. Therefore, we propose two steps solution for the RIS phase shift design. In the first step, the RIS elements are grouped into two distinct groups to form two sub-surfaces. The first sub-surface encompasses L_m DP RIS elements while the second sub-surface encompasses the rest of $L - L_m$ elements. In this case, the noiseless received signal at the chosen antenna index in (13) becomes

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_n = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_1}} \mathbf{g}_{n_v, l}^T \bar{\Psi}_l \bar{\mathbf{h}}_l + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_2}} \mathbf{g}_{n_v, l}^T \bar{\Psi}_l \bar{\mathbf{h}}_l \\ \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_1}} \mathbf{g}_{n_h, l}^T \bar{\Psi}_l \bar{\mathbf{h}}_l + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_2}} \mathbf{g}_{n_h, l}^T \bar{\Psi}_l \bar{\mathbf{h}}_l \end{bmatrix} x_k, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{m_1} = \{1, \dots, L_m\}$ and $\mathcal{L}_{m_2} = \{L_m + 1, \dots, L\}$ represent the sets of elements in the first and second sub-surfaces which, for simplicity, are chosen in a consecutive order. In the second step, the phase shifts of the elements in the first sub-surface are chosen to solely maximize the signal strength as well as control the phase shift of the resultant received signal at the vertical antenna branch. In a similar way, the second sub-surface aims at maximizing the signal strength and controlling the phase shift of the resultant received signal

at the horizontal antenna branch. For the sake of simplicity, we assume perfect channel state information (CSI) at the RIS, which is possible using RIS channel estimation techniques and feedback through a control link to the RIS. In this case, the phase shifts for the n th spatial modulated and m th polarization modulated symbols become

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{l_v}(n, m) &= \begin{cases} \arg\{g_{n_v, l_v} h_{l_v}\} + \beta_m/2, & l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_1} \\ \arg\{g_{n_v, l_v} h_{l_v}\} - \beta_m/2, & l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_2} \end{cases} \\ \phi_{l_h}(n, m) &= \begin{cases} \arg\{g_{n_h, l_h} h_{l_h}\} + \beta_m/2, & l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_1} \\ \arg\{g_{n_h, l_h} h_{l_h}\} - \beta_m/2, & l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_2} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Thus, the noiseless received signal at the n receiver antenna becomes

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_n = \begin{bmatrix} a_n e^{j\frac{\beta_m}{2}} + c_n \\ b_n e^{-j\frac{\beta_m}{2}} + d_n \end{bmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

where a_n and b_n represent the co-polarization signal that arises from the first and second sub-surface on the vertical and horizontal components, respectively, as

$$\begin{aligned} a_n &= \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_1}} |g_{n_v, l_v} h_{l_v}| + |g_{n_v, l_h} h_{l_h}|, \\ b_n &= \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_2}} |g_{n_h, l_v} h_{l_v}| + |g_{n_h, l_h} h_{l_h}|, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

and c_n and d_n represent the cross-polarization interference that arises from the first sub-surface on the horizontal signal and from the second sub-surface on the vertical signal, respectively, as

$$\begin{aligned} c_n &= \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_2}} e^{j\phi_{l_v}} g_{n_v, l_v} h_{l_v} + e^{j\phi_{l_h}} g_{n_v, l_h} h_{l_h}, \\ d_n &= \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{m_1}} e^{j\phi_{l_v}} g_{n_h, l_v} h_{l_v} + e^{j\phi_{l_h}} g_{n_h, l_h} h_{l_h}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Note that the co-polarization components in (18) are superimposed coherently. However, the cross-polarization components in (19) are superimposed incoherently; thus it can be ignored as

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_n \approx \begin{bmatrix} a_n e^{j\frac{\beta_m}{2}} \\ b_n e^{-j\frac{\beta_m}{2}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

where the phase shift difference of β_m is fulfilled. Furthermore, the grouping process of the RIS elements into two distinct sub-surfaces allows the control of the amplitude ratio between the vertical and horizontal signal; in particular, the choice of L_m directly impacts ϑ_m .

A RIS grouping scheme that achieves any amplitude ratio can be obtained by exhaustive search as

$$\arg \min_{L_m \in \{0, \dots, L\}} \left| \tan \vartheta_m - \frac{|\mu_{n_v}|}{|\mu_{n_h}|} \right|. \quad (21)$$

Alternately, a lower complexity solution can be obtained by assuming the co-polarization components that arise from elements in distinct sub-surfaces along the vertical and horizontal branches are approximately equal as, $\mathbb{E}[a_n]/\mathbb{E}[b_n] =$

$L_m/(L - L_m) = \tan \vartheta_m$. Therefore, a heuristic RIS grouping scheme that achieves a particular amplitude ratio can be obtained as

$$L_m = \frac{L \tan \vartheta_m}{\tan \vartheta_m + 1}. \quad (22)$$

IV. DATA DETECTION

A. Maximum Likelihood Detector

The optimum detector maximum likelihood (ML) that jointly performs the spatial, polarization and PSK demodulation is

$$\arg \min_{\substack{n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ m \in \{1, \dots, M\} \\ k \in \{1, \dots, K\}}} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{G}\Psi_{(n,m)}\mathbf{h}x_k\|^2, \quad (23)$$

where $\Psi_{(n,m)}$ is the RIS phase shift matrix for the n th spatial and m th polarization modulated symbols as shown in (16). However, the ML detector requires the CSI at the receiver. Furthermore, the ML detector requires searching over all the possible (n, m, k) tuples; thus, the computational complexity of the ML detector is proportional to $\mathcal{O}(NMK)$.

B. Low Complexity Detector

To avoid the CSI requirement as well as the high computational complexity of the ML detector a low-complexity greedy detector (GD) which operates in a sequential fashion starting from the spatial demodulation, then the polarization demodulation and after that the PSK demodulation can be utilized. First, perform spatial demodulation based on the antenna index with maximum signal strength as

$$\arg \max_{n \in \{1, \dots, N\}} \|\mathbf{y}_n\|^2. \quad (24)$$

Second, compute the normalized Stokes sub-vector at the detected receiver antenna index for polarization demodulation as

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}}_{\mathbf{y}_n} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{y}_n^H \mathbf{y}_n} \begin{bmatrix} |y_{n_u}|^2 - |y_{n_v}|^2 \\ 2\Re\{y_{n_u}y_{n_v}^*\} \\ -2\Im\{y_{n_u}y_{n_v}^*\} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

Then, polarization demodulation can be obtained by selecting the symbol with minimum distance to the corresponding Stokes sub-vector as

$$\arg \min_{m \in \{1, \dots, M\}} \|\bar{\mathbf{s}}_{\mathbf{y}_n} - \bar{\mathbf{s}}_m\|^2, \quad (26)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{s}}_m$ represents the Stokes sub-vector of the m th polarization modulated symbol. Finally, the demodulated polarization symbol is utilized to equalize the received signal. Then, the PSK symbol can be detected based on the minimum distance as

$$\arg \min_{k \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \|\mathbf{z}^H \mathbf{y}_n - x_k\|^2, \quad (27)$$

where $\mathbf{z} = [\sin \vartheta_m e^{j\frac{\beta_m}{2}}, \cos \vartheta_m e^{-j\frac{\beta_m}{2}}]^T$ is computed by using the detected polarization symbol in (26). Note that the sequential low-complexity detector does not need CSI at the receiver. Furthermore, given that the detection process is performed over three sequential stages, the computational complexity is proportional to $\mathcal{O}(N + M + K)$.

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of RIS elements (L)	64
Number of RX antennas (N)	8
Noise power (σ^2)	-90 dBm
Polarization correlation factors (p_t , p_r , and p_{ris})	0.1
Spatial correlation factors (δ_r , δ_{ris_y} and δ_{ris_z})	0.1
XPD factors (κ_1 and κ_2)	5 dB
XPI factors (χ_t^{-1} , χ_{ris}^{-1} , and χ_r^{-1})	30 dB
Phase offsets (φ_t , φ_{ris} , and φ_r)	0°
TX Location	$[0, 0, 5] m$
RIS Location	$[30, 30, 3] m$
RX Location	$[70, 5, 1.5] m$

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed RIS-JPSM scheme. The simulation parameters are as presented in Table I. Without loss of generality, we employ a reference path loss model with path loss exponents for the transmitter to RIS and RIS to receiver channels of 2.8 and 3.3, respectively, while a reference point is taken at $1m$ separation distance of 20 dB path loss is considered. Moreover, the geometric orientation difference angles between the transmitter and RIS and between the RIS to receiver are randomly generated from a uniform distribution; $\theta_t, \theta_{ris} \sim \mathcal{U}[0, 2\pi]$, while the performance is averaged out.

We compare the performance of the proposed scheme relative to the conventional RIS-SM scheme [8] which deploys a RIS of $2L$ SP elements and receiver ULA of $2N$ SP antennas; thus, we create a fair comparison. The RIS-SM scheme allows the transmission of $\log_2[2N] + \log_2[K]$ bpcu. Therefore, if the proposed RIS-JPSM employs a similar PSK scheme as that of RIS-SM and BPolSK, it achieves an equivalent data rate to that of the RIS-SM scheme. In Fig. 2a, the bit-error-rate (BER) performances of the proposed RIS-JPSM and RIS-SM scheme are shown for both the ML and GD detectors. The RIS phase shift design of the RIS-JPSM scheme is obtained using the heuristic approach as in (22). It is clear that the performance of the proposed scheme is better than the RIS-SM scheme given an equivalent data rate of both schemes, which is attributed to the polarization diversity introduced by deploying DP RIS and receiver.

Furthermore, a fundamental advantage of the proposed RIS-JPSM is that it can enhance the data rate by utilizing higher-order polarization modulation schemes. In Fig. 2b, the BER performances of RIS-JPSM with higher polarization modulation schemes and exhaustive RIS phase shift design approach are compared to that of the RIS-SM scheme, while both schemes employ QPSK modulation scheme. The performance of RIS-JPSM with QPolSK and ML detector is better than that of RIS-SM; however, the performance of RIS-SM is better than the rest of the RIS-JPSM schemes. Note that the RIS-JPSM schemes achieve higher data rate performances than those of RIS-SM. Thus, we utilize the effective throughput as a comparison metric between the RIS-JPSM and RIS-SM schemes. The effective throughput is defined as the number of correct bits received per channel use; thus, it combines both the BER and data rate performances in a single metric [17]. In Fig. 2c, the effective throughput of RIS-JPSM and RIS-SM

Fig. 2: Performances comparison between RIS-JPSM and RIS-SM schemes versus the the transmitted power. In (a) both schemes achieve equivalent data rate, in (b) RIS-JPSM has higher data rate with respect to the RIS-SM, and in (c) the effective throughput for the comparison in (b) is shown.

Fig. 3: BER performances of the exhaustive and heuristic RIS tuning methods are shown versus the number of RIS elements. schemes are shown given the GD is utilized. It is clear that the proposed RIS-JPSM enhances the effective throughput in comparison to the RIS-SM scheme.

In Fig. 3, the impact of the RIS phase shift design scheme is studied, where the BER performances of the exhaustive search method in (21) and the heuristic tuning method in (22) are shown versus the number of RIS elements, at $P_t = 30$ dBm. The performance of the exhaustive search method is better than that of the heuristic method; however, the heuristic one still can provide satisfactory performances.

VI. CONCLUSION

We proposed a RIS-based joint spatial and polarization modulation scheme. In this scheme, a RIS of DP reflecting elements encodes the reflected waves to modulate extra information data in terms of the receiver antenna index as well as the polarization state of the received signal. Furthermore, exhaustive and heuristic RIS phase shift design solutions are proposed. Moreover, an optimum maximum likelihood detector and a low-complexity greedy detector are formulated. The proposed scheme allows data rate enhancement in comparison to the conventional RIS-based spatial modulation schemes, by operating higher-order polarization modulation scheme.

REFERENCES

[1] M. Di Renzo et al., "Smart Radio Environments Empowered by Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces: How It Works, State of Research, and The Road Ahead," in *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas*

in Communications, vol. 38, no. 11, pp. 2450-2525, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/JSAC.2020.3007211.

[2] C. Huang et al., "Holographic MIMO Surfaces for 6G Wireless Networks: Opportunities, Challenges, and Trends," in *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 118-125, October 2020

[3] C. Guo et al., "Advances on exploiting polarization in wireless communications: Channels, technologies, and applications," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 125-166, 1st Quart., 2017

[4] Y. Han et al., "Dual-Polarized RIS-Assisted Mobile Communications," in *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 591-606, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TWC.2021.3098521.

[5] H. Yang et al., "A programmable metasurface with dynamic polarization, scattering and focusing control," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 6, Oct. 2016, Art. no. 35692. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep35692>

[6] W. Yan et al., "Passive Beamforming and Information Transfer via Large Intelligent Surface," in *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 533-537, April 2020, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2019.2961670.

[7] A. E. Canbilen et al., "Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-Assisted Space Shift Keying," in *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 1495-1499, Sept. 2020, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2020.2994930.

[8] E. Basar, "Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-Based Index Modulation: A New Beyond MIMO Paradigm for 6G," in *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 3187-3196, May 2020, doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2020.2971486.

[9] S. Guo et al., "Reflecting modulation," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 38, no. 11, pp. 2548-2561, 2020.

[10] S. Lin et al., "Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces with reflection pattern modulation: Beamforming design and performance analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp 741-754, 2020.

[11] E. Ibrahim, et al., "Binary Polarization Shift Keying With Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces," in *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 908-912, May 2022, doi: 10.1109/LWC.2022.3149618.

[12] Emil Björnson, Jakob Hoydis and Luca Sanguinetti (2017), "Massive MIMO Networks: Spectral, Energy, and Hardware Efficiency", *Foundations and Trends® in Signal Processing: Vol. 11, No. 3-4*, pp 154-655. DOI: 10.1561/20000000093.

[13] M. Coldrey, "Modeling and Capacity of Polarized MIMO Channels," *VTC Spring 2008 - IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference*, Marina Bay, Singapore, 2008, pp. 440-444, doi: 10.1109/VETECS.2008.103.

[14] S. L. Loyka, "Channel capacity of MIMO architecture using the exponential correlation matrix," in *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 369-371, Sept. 2001, doi: 10.1109/4234.951380.

[15] P. Henarejos et al., "3-D Polarized Modulation: System Analysis and Performance," in *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 66, no. 11, pp. 5305-5316, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2018.2850814.

[16] N. J. A. Sloane. *Tables of Spherical Codes*. Accessed: Jun. 28, 2018. [Online]. Available: NeilSloane.com/packings

[17] J. C. Estrada-Jiménez et al., "Partial-Data Superimposed Training With Data Precoding for OFDM Systems," in *IEEE Transactions on Broadcasting*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 234-244, June 2019, doi: 10.1109/TBC.2018.2874542.